

GENRES OF FAIRY TALES

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A fairy tale is the most ancient and popular example of artistic prose in the folklore. Each of us grows up hearing fairy tales from childhood. Adults tell stories to entertain children, and children themselves start telling small stories when they grow up and start going to school. The stories that these children tell each other are partly what they heard from adults, and partly what they tell themselves. Researcher Yu. The Sokolovs must have meant this: they regretted that "the stories told by the children to each other were almost never recorded." If we look at the tellers of the collected folk tales, we will see that most of them were told by adults. Fairy tales have an artistic-compositional construction specific to their genre nature. They are created and performed within the framework of the same artistic forms. Introduction, beginning, knot, epic adventure and conclusion form the basis of the compositional device of a fairy tale. The beginning of fairy tales with a traditional introduction is a common feature of fairy tales of all peoples of the world. The task of the traditional introduction is to attract the attention of the listeners to one point, prepare them to listen to the tale.

Usually, the introductory parts of fairy tales are in the form of decorated prose passages, which express information about time and place. For example, we can see this situation in the introduction to the tale "Gulpari". Below is an excerpt from it: "Once there is, once there is no, the wolf is a hawk, the fox is a madman, the goose is a trumpeter, a duck is a trumpeter, a turtle is a scale, and a frog is in debt." In ancient times, there was a country called Gulzor. In this country there lived an old man and an old woman who had no equal in wisdom."

The introduction of some fairy tales is connected to the beginning of the fairy tale only in some cases, and at other times it remains independent. In a fairy tale, the beginning is a constant element in the subject line, but it is not related to the development of the subject, but does not motivate the organization of the action. It gives information about the characters. It informs about the time and place of the events taking place in the plot line. The beginning acquires vagueness and generality in the direction of the subject. "When there is, there is no. When you are hungry, you are full. "There was a king in ancient times." The beginnings always represent mutually exclusive terms. In them, the location of the events and events is unknown, the name is not mentioned, uncertainty reigns in them: "One city, one country" is only emphasized.

Tale beginnings are long or short according to their appearance, and the story gives vague, general and abstract information about the future place and time of events. Sometimes it is observed that the beginning of the fairy tale is combined with reality: "Once upon a time, there were three heroic brothers who set out on a long journey to try their luck." Beginnings in such a situation prepare the ground for the acceleration and intensification of the development of the events in the fairy tale, and the intensification of conflicts.

It is worth noting that the beginning is not an exposition, but opens a way for it - exposition, gives place. The beginning does not concern the subject, but in a fairy tale, the subject begins with exposition. Exposition is directly related to the knot of the work; The movement of events, conflict and development of events that make up the subject line begins with the exposition: "The king had an only son - years passed, and the king's son grew up. One day he saw a girl in a dream and fell in love with her. It is said that the news that the king has an only son gives him the motivation to see a girl in a dream. At the same time, it became a reference to the development of the subject - the conflict that forms the basis of the epic adventure.

took storytelling seriously. Folklore works of the epic genre, such as epics, fairy tales, and tales, are told by professional performers who have specific epic memory, epic knowledge, and performance potential, i.e., special training. Narratives and legends are performed by the general public. Noting that the lack of a professional narrator is one of the unique features of the myth genre, K.Imomov wrote that "the legend does not have to be told by a professional storyteller or storyteller, but a person who has heard and knows can tell the story in any form he wants."

Folklorist U. Jumanazarov notes that "the lack of professional narrators and the character of a wide public performance is an important feature of the genres of legends and narratives.

Folklorist M. Joraev, while noting that the people who recite texts related to the genres of legends, narratives and oral stories, are not suitable for professional performances that popularize folklore works, makes the following important conclusion: also tells legends or stories. But any person who writes works belonging to the genres of educational prose (myth, legend, narrative, oral story - U.S.) cannot tell folk tales at the level of a professional storyteller. In conclusion, we can say that we considered and analyzed the division of fairy tales into several types in the process of studying the topic of fairy tales.

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